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Letter to Editor

A healthy way to improve hypertension

Letter to Editor

Miguel Devronsky proposed in 1970's a theory explaining mechanism of action of ingested pure protein; so-called protein-diet, as follows: 1. Ingested pure protein is decomposed into mixture of amino acids by gastrointestinal proteolytic enzymes; pepsin, trypsin, chymotrypsin, etc. Mixture of amino acids enters the liver via the portal vein. The liver resynthesizes protein with the amino acid mixture consuming synthesis-energy, which is supplied by decomposition of unnecessary tissues like hypodermic fat, intravascular atheroma, etc. In short, ingestion of pure protein improves atheroscleroses of arteries. It is well established that the main cause of hypertension is arterial atherosclerosis. In conclusion, oral ingestion of pure protein, e.g., casein, can be an easy way of improving and preventing atheroscleroses.

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